

Supplemental information

Figure S1: a) A flow-through part of the cell with disassembled felts and CNT layer, and b) a detail of the 3D assembled sandwich-type electrode with CNTs.

Figure S2: Assembled measuring apparatus for electrochemical testing of carbon nanostructured materials in flow-through electrochemical VRFB single cell.

Figure S3: Electrochemical cell with pressure sensors connected to both inlets for pressure drop measurements.

Figure S4: Charge-discharge steps for the individual tested materials under three linear velocities: a) untreated ground graphite felt electrode (UT-GFE), b) thermally-treated ground graphite felt electrode (TT-GFE), c) multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), d) carboxylated multiwalled carbon nanotubes (f-MWCNTs), and e) few-walled carbon nanotubes (FWCNTs). The applied currents for charging and discharging are identical to those in Figure 6.

Figure S5: Polarization curves for the tested materials obtained at linear velocities of a) 2.5 cm/min, b) 7.3 cm/min, and c) 14.6 cm/min.